

A Appendix: Survey instrument

A.1 Screening Survey Question

Q1 When was your most recent stay in an Airbnb property?

- Past three days
- Past week
- Past month
- Past six months
- Past year
- More than a year ago
- I have never stayed in Airbnb before.

A.2 Main Survey

Experiences with smart home devices

Q1 How long was your recent Airbnb stay?

- 1-3 days
- 4-7 days
- More than 7 days

Q2 Which of the following devices do you own or regularly use? (Select all that apply)

- Smart Remote Controls (e.g., Samsung SmartThings Hub)
- Smart Lighting Solutions (e.g., Samsung SmartThings Hub, Philips Hue),
- Smart Voice-Activated Products (e.g., Amazon Echo, Apple Home),
- Smart Door Locks (e.g., Yale Assure Lock, Honeywell Smart Locks)
- Smart Toys (e.g., iDog, Sphero Mini, Makey Makey)
- Smart Home Appliances (e.g., LG Smart ThinQ Washer/Dryer /Refrigerator Samsung)
- Smart Home Sensors (e.g., Hue Motion Sensor, Samsung SmartThings, OxyLED)
- Smart Home Utilities (e.g., Nest Learning Thermostat, Blossom Smart Watering Controller)
- Smart Window Solutions (e.g., Smart Tint, Smart Door and Window Sensors)
- Smart Home Surveillance Cameras (e.g., Arlo Smart Camera, Nest Indoor Cam)
- I do not use smart home devices regularly

Q3 How long have you been using smart home devices?

- Less than 6 months
- Between 1-2 years

- Between 2-3 years

- More than 3 years

Privacy Negotiation Definition *You will see three scenarios about interacting with Internet of Things (IoT) devices in your potential Airbnb stays. During the stay, you may find some IoT devices in or outside the Airbnb property, raise privacy concerns to the Airbnb host, and seek a possible solution. We refer to this process as “privacy negotiation.”*

Storyboard-based Questions

Q1 As a guest, have you ever experienced and/or can you expect this situation to happen to you during your stay at an Airbnb? (1 = I have experienced and can imagine this happening again in the future, 2 = I have experienced it but I cannot imagine this happening again in the future, 3 = I have not experienced it but I can imagine this happening to me in the future, 4 = I have not experienced this and I cannot imagine this happening to me in the future)

- I have experienced and can imagine this happening again in the future.

- I have experienced it but I cannot imagine this happening again in the future.

- I have not experienced it but I can imagine this happening to me in the future.

- I have not experienced this and I cannot imagine this happening to me in the future.

Q2 From the guest’s perspective, how effective or ineffective does this privacy negotiation shown in the storyboard address privacy concerns related to the camera? (1 = Very effective, 2 = Somewhat effective, 3 = Somewhat ineffective, 4 = Very ineffective)

- Very effective

- Somewhat effective

- Somewhat ineffective

- Very ineffective

Q3 From the guest’s perspective, how practical or impractical is it to use this privacy negotiation shown in the storyboard? (1 = Very practical, 2 = Somewhat practical, 3 = Somewhat impractical, 4 = Very impractical)

- Very practical

- Somewhat practical

- Somewhat impractical

- Very impractical

Q4 From the guest’s perspective, how likely or unlikely would you like to use this privacy negotiation in the future? (1 = Very likely, 2 = Somewhat likely, 3 = Somewhat unlikely, 4 = Very unlikely)

- Very likely
- Somewhat likely
- Somewhat unlikely
- Very unlikely

Q5 If you were in Jane's situation, would you negotiate in a similar manner as depicted in the storyboard? Why?

Q6 If you were in Jane's situation, how can this negotiation strategy be made more effective to address your needs? For example, what would you like to change or add?

Q7 If you were in Jane's situation, are you satisfied with the outcome of the privacy negotiation as portrayed in the storyboard? If not, what actions do you intend to take next?

Demographic Questions

Q1 How do you describe yourself?

- Man
- Woman
- Non-binary

Q2 How old are you?

- 18-24 years old
- 25-34 years old
- 35-44 years old
- 45-54 years old
- 55+ years old

Q3 What is your highest education level?

- High school or below
- Bachelor degree
- Master degree
- Doctoral degree
- Prefer not to answer

Q4 Please select the statement that best describes your comfort level with computing technology.

- Ultra Nerd: I build my own computers- run my own servers- code my own apps. I'm basically Mr. Robot.
- Technically Savvy: I know my way around a computer pretty well. When anyone in my family needs technical help- I'm the one they call.
- Average User: I know enough to get by.
- Luddite: Technology scares me! I only use it when I have to.

Q5 Indicate the extent to which you agree or disagree with the following statements [1=Strongly Disagree, 7=Strongly Agree]

- In general, I believe privacy is important.
- In today's world, privacy does not exist anymore.
- I'm concerned that "smart" devices collect too much personal information.
- I'm confident in my ability to control how much personal information I share online and through my phone.

Q6 What best describes your employment status over the last three months?

- Working full-time
- Working part-time
- Unemployed and looking for work
- A homemaker or stay-at-home parent
- Student
- Retired
- Other

Q7 What is your current marital status?

- Married
- Living with a partner
- Widowed
- Divorced/Separated
- Never been married